

Council for
BRITISH ARCHAEOLOGY
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Hon. Secretary: MR. P. J. FOWLER, M.A., F.S.A.

Secretary: MISS B. DE CARDI, F.S.A.

21st April, 1973

Dear Andrew,

I raced into the office this morning and have now produced the revised application for Oman of which I enclose two copies. I have sent four off to the Chargé d'Affaires with the attached note of explanation. Do let me know how things go when you have a chance of seeing him.

Renewed congratulations on your Directorship!

Yours

A. G. Williamson, Esq., M.A.,
West End, Wootton,
Woodstock, Oxon.